

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

THE STATE OF IRRIGATED SOILS IN THE KURA-ARAKS LOWLAND OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

Irrigated soils in the Kura-Araks Lowland are subject to irrigation-induced erosion, natural water and wind erosion, and salinization. Of the 2,098,800 hectares of agricultural land in the lowland, the areas of land subject to erosion and salinization reach 333,600 and 373,398 hectares, respectively. The relationship between irrigation-induced erosion and soil type (gray sierozems, meadow sierozems, and graycinnamonic soils), irrigation furrow slope, irrigation water salinity (0.15–0.95 g/L), and water flow (0.8–1.4 L/s) was studied. It was found that soil erosion and salinization lead to changes in soil density and porosity, as well as a decrease in humus and nutrient content. Certain changes in soil texture also occur. The area of land susceptible to erosion from heavy, moderate, and light rainfall is estimated at 57,700, 24,400, and 15,300 hectares, respectively. Measures to combat soil erosion and salinization are discussed. Main types of soil degradation in the Kura-Araks lowland of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: irrigation-induced erosion, wind erosion, salinization, slope of the surface, degree of erosion, sierozems, meadowsierozemic soils, light graycinnamonic soils.

1. INTRODUCTION

Land degradation is an urgent problem for Azerbaijan, as well as for other arid. Land degradation results in lower soil fertility and, thus, in declining living regions [2, 5, 8, 12] standards of people. This process is especially intensive in the Kura-Araks Lowland. The main types of degradation are irrigation-induced erosion, natural water and wind erosion, and salinization [17]. The Kura-Araks Lowland is the cotton, grain, legume, and fruit base of Azerbaijan. The study of the factors and regularities of the anthropogenic soil degradation is necessary for adequate use and protection of soil resources in this area [7, 17].

2. OBJECTS AND METHODS

The area of agricultural land in the Kura-Araks Lowland is 2098.8 thousand ha. The absolute heights of the lowland vary from 28 to 101 m a.s.l. This territory is a slightly dissected undulating plain composed of alluvial heavy loams, clays, sands, and gravelly sediments. The surface inclination varies from 0.0001° to 0.100° in the western elevated part of the lowland and from 0.001° to 0.065° within the irrigated area on the lower accumulative plains of the Kura-Araks Lowland. The studied area is characterized by a subtropical climate with a dry and hot summer. The mean annual temperature is 12–13°C, and the mean January temperature is +3.9–5.2°C, so the soils do not freeze. The sum of active (>10°C) daily temperatures reaches 4000–5200 degreedays, the mean annual precipitation does not exceed 180–450 mm, and the humidity factor varies within 0.3–0.15 [4, 6, 10, 15].

Field studies were performed on key sites in the Mugan'-Sal'yansk, Mil'sk, Karabakh, and Shirvan steppes of the Kura-Araks Lowland. We studied sierozems (Calcisols), meadowsierozemic soils (Gleyic Calcisols), light gray cinnamonic soils (Haplic Kastanozems), and their irrigated analogues, which represent the main soil resources of the area.

Sierozemic soils (Calcisols) are allocated to gently sloping plains with mesodepressions at heights from

11 to 200 m a.s.l. (mainly, in the Shirvan and Mugan'-Sal'yansk steppes). They are developed from marine and mud volcanic loamy, clay loamy, and clayey deposits and from the alluvial sediments. The natural plant cover is represented by the grass-wormwood-caragana associations. The sierozems are saline soils: the salt content in the layer of 0–2 m is from 1.5 to

3.0%. The salinization is of the chloride-sulfate type. The humus content in the upper 25 cm varies from 1.61 to 2.15%.

Meadow sierozemic soils (Gleyic Calcisols) are allocated to inclined plains, footslopes, and mesodepressions at heights from 11 to 300 m a.s.l.; they are widespread on the Mugan'-Sal'yansk, Mil'sk, Shirvan, and Karabakh steppes. These soils are developed from colluvial and alluvial loesslike loams under wormwood-ephemeral plant communities. The soils are often calcareous and contain soluble salts (0.34–1.06%) in the upper 2 m. The salinization is of the chloride-sulfate type. The humus content in the upper cm is 2.00–2.10%.

Light graycinnamonic soils (the type of mountainous gray cinnamonic soils) are developed from the Upper Quaternary clays and heavy clays of alluvial origin at heights from 70 to 300 m a.s.l. under conditions similar to those of the chestnut soils. They are allocated to dry steppes and semideserts on the foothills of the Minor and Great Caucasian ranges. The plant cover is composed of the grassy-wormwood-ephemeral vegetation. The soils are often calcareous and slightly saline (0.11–0.60%). The salinization is of the chloride-sulfate type. The humus content in the upper 25 cm is 2.15–2.48%.

The upper boundary of carbonate accumulation in the irrigated sierozems, meadow sierozemic, and light gray cinnamonic soils is deeper as compared to the rain-fed soils. The meadow sierozemic and light gray cinnamonic soils are also characterized by the presence of gypsum in the deep layers. Irrigation-induced erosion and natural water erosion were studied in the field.

Running irrigation water was sampled from irrigation furrows 5, 15, 60, 120, 180, and 240 min after the beginning of irrigation and in the last hours of irrigation in three replicates according to the method suggested by M.S. Kuznetsov. Morphometric measurements of the appearing rills were also performed [11].

The irrigation water flows were measured at the beginning and end of the furrows using Thomson's gauges (45°); the flow velocity in the furrows was determined with the use of a coloring liquid and timer and regulated with polyethylene blankets. The wind erosion was studied according to Zaslavskii [16]. Archive data of the Institute of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan were used to judge the degree of soil salinization [3]. The areas of degraded soils were calculated according to a digitized map of soil degradation in the Kura–Araks Lowland developed by E.A. Kurbanov (Institute of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan) with the use of Access–(ArcGIS) software [9].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Kura–Araks Lowland is subdivided into five physiographic regions (steppes): the Mugan'–Sal'yansk, Mil'sk, Karabakh, Shirvan, and Gyandzha

steppes. The Shirvan Steppe is found on the left bank of the Kura River; the Gyandzha, Karabakh, and Mil'sk steppes occupy the Kura–Araks Interfluvium; the Mugansk Steppe is found to the south of the Aras River; and the Sal'yansk Steppe occupies the right bank of the Kura River in its lower reaches. Each of the steppes is characterized by a specific climate, topography, soils, and vegetation.

Irrigation-induced and wind erosion are widespread in the Kura–Araks

Lowland. Irrigation-induced erosion is typical of the entire semidesert zone and piedmonts with an inclination of more than 0.003. Wind erosion is developed along the Kura River (on the southeastern parts of the Shirvan and Sal'yansk steppes) and in the western part of the lowland. The arid climate, coarse soil texture, strong local winds, and extreme grazing loads favor the development of wind erosion (Table 1). The degree of erosion was evaluated on the basis of the following diagnostic criteria: the decrease in the thickness of the humus horizon and humus content in the soil profile, the decrease in the pool of soil nutrients, the changes in the topsoil texture and flow rates, the inclination of the surface, the intensity of the wind erosion, the thinning of the grass cover and crops, the total salt content in the top fertile layer, the soil reaction (pH of the water extract), etc.

Table 1.

Area of eroded lands in the Kura–Aras Lowland (2009, thousand ha)

Region	Total area	Total area of eroded lands	Areas with different types of erosion				
			rainstorm			Irrigation-induced	wind
			degree of erosion				
weak	mediums	strong					
Mugan'-Sal'yansk massif	871.1	131.2	21.7	11.7	-	36.2	61.6
Shirvan Steppe	508.0	116.9	16.0	8.3	8.6	41.5	42.5
Mil'sk Steppe	477.9	29.7	1.9	0.6	-	24.5	2.7
Karabakh Steppe	241.8	55.8	18.1	3.8	6.7	24.9	2.3
Total	2098.8	333.6	57.7	24.4	15.3	127.1	109.1

Water erosion. More than 64% of the irrigated lands in the lowland are allocated to inclined surfaces. Three types of irrigation-induced erosion can be distinguished:

(1) sheet erosion of the topmost horizons of irrigated soils under the impact of both irrigation water and rainstorms;

(2) rill erosion, including bottom and side erosion of the irrigation network followed by the formation of deeper hollows and ravines;

(3) destruction of the irrigation network with the removal of topsoil horizons and the formation of mudflows. Rainstorm erosion is especially intensive on winter pastures with slopes of 5°–7° upon overgrazing, when the barren soil surface makes the soil susceptible to erosion. The soil loss tolerance increases with an increase in the contents of clay, humus, and bivalent cations. Rainstorm erosion is especially pronounced on

sierozems of the Shirvan steppe (8.6 thousand ha). These soils are developed under thin vegetation cover and are characterized by a low content of the clay (<0.001 mm) fraction (11.0–18.0%) and humus (1.3–1.6%). Soil washout takes place under the impact of heavy rains in the spring and fall seasons. In the case of irrigation-induced erosion, three zones of the washout, stabilization, and accumulation of sediments are formed along the furrows in dependence on the local topography and the length of the furrow. The uneven surface of irrigated plots enhances the washout and accumulation of sediments. Soil erosion in furrows is mainly seen in their most inclined parts.

Data on the intensity of the irrigation-induced erosion in dependence on the slope of the surface and the water discharge rates are given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Irrigation-induced erosion as dependent on the slope of the surface and irrigation water discharge				
Slope; soil	Furrow length, m	Water discharge in furrow, L/s	Water turbidity, g/L	Soil washout per one irrigation, t/ha
0.006, heavy loamy light sierozemic	200	0.6	8.25	2.26
		0.8	13.67	4.68
		1.0	16.82	6.41
		1.2	21.54	8.84
0.018, heavy loamy light sierozemic	200	0.2	9.44	2.78
		0.4	15.28	6.42
		0.6	20.65	10.74
		0.8	26.76	14.86
0.012, medium loamy typical sierozemic	200	0.4	13.80	2.23
		0.6	19.63	3.48
		0.8	23.84	5.20
		1.0	26.47	7.12
0.003, medium loamy meadowsi erozemic	250	0.8	4.56	2.44
		1.0	5.12	2.98
		1.2	7.24	3.45
		1.4	9.10	4.16
0.020, medium loamy light graycinna monic (chestnut)	150	0.2	9.13	2.54
		0.4	15.56	5.82
		0.6	19.34	9.16
		0.8	24.78	13.40

They show that the soil erosion depends on the slope gradient, water discharge, and soil loss tolerance. Thus, in the case of a furrow gradient of 0.006, water discharge rates of 0.6 and 1.2 L/s, and a furrow length of 200 m, the turbidity of the discharged water on heavy loamy light sierozems reaches 8.25 and 21.54 g/L, which corresponds to the washout of 2.26 and 8.84 t/ha, respectively. At a higher slope gradient (0.018), water discharge rates of 0.2 and 0.8 L/s, and a furrow length of 200 m, the turbidity constitutes 9.44 and 26.76 g/L, which corresponds to the washout of 2.78 and 14.86 t/ha, respectively. The smallest soil washout per one irrigation (2.44–4.16 t/ha) is seen at a slope gradient of 0.003, a furrow length of up to 250 m, and a water discharge rate of 0.8–1.4 L/s.

In the case of furrow erosion, the texture of the surface soil horizon becomes coarser due to the removal of the clay fractions. These fractions tend to accumulate in distant (lower) parts of the furrows.

The worsening of the structural state of eroded soils exerts a negative impact on other soil properties and regimes. Disaggregation and compaction of irrigated soils often lead to the soil overcompaction. This is especially the case for the plow horizons, though some soil compaction takes place also in the deeper layers. The nonuniform soil texture on the fields complicates agricultural works and crop growing. Thin surface crusts are developed in the furrows, whereas the layers

of accumulated sediments on the soil surface may have considerable thickness. Upon drying, these irrigation deposits are transformed into cemented surface horizons with high bulk density preventing the development of plants.

Irrigation-induced erosion on the light gray-cinnamonic and meadow -sierozemic soils leads to an increase in the soil bulk density up to from 1.09–1.46 and 1.20–1.58 g/cm³, respectively; the hydraulic conductivity of these soils decreases to 1.6–1.7 and 1.2–1.5 mm/min, respectively. The bulk density of the soil in the eroded part of the furrows is somewhat lower, because the less compact lower soil horizon becomes exposed to the surface.

The contents of humus, nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in the suspended sediments are higher than those in the plow layer. For example, in the light gray-cinnamonic soil, the humus content in the upper 25 cm is 2.00–2.15%; in the suspended sediments washed out from the soil, it is 0.50–0.84% higher and reaches 2.84% in the case of the water discharge rate of 0.2 L/s (Table 3). The contents of humus, total nitrogen, and phosphorus in the suspended sediments at the ends of the furrows (where the rate of water discharge decreases) are 20–30% higher than those in the suspended sediments at the beginning of the furrows with the higher rates of water discharge.

Table 3.

Humus and nutrient contents in the washed out sediments					
Slope; soil	Water discharge	Humus	Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Potassium
		%			
0.006, heavy loamy light sierozemic	0.6	3.00	0.20	0.23	2.54
	0.8	2.92	0.19	0.23	2.50
	1.0	2.80	0.19	0.22	2.51
	1.2	2.80	1.2	2 1.2	2.50
0.018, heavy loamy light sierozemic	0.2	2.11	0.16	0.19	2.49
	0.4	2.05	0.16	0.18	2.52
	0.6	2.05	0.15	0.18	2.50
	0.8	1.98	0.15	0.17	2.51
0.012, medium loamy typical sierozemic	0.4	3.20	0.22	0.27	2.68
	0.6	3.00	0.21	0.25	2.64
	0.8	3.00	0.19	0.25	2.66
	1.0	2.90	0.19	0.25	2.64
0.020, medium loamy light graycinnamonic (chestnut)	0.2	2.84	0.16	0.18	2.67
	0.4	2.72	0.14	0.17	2.69
	0.6	2.53	0.13	0.17	2.65
	0.8	2.50	0.13	0.16	2.68

The evaluation of the humus and nutrient losses shows that they are in direct correlation with the water discharge. Thus, upon the surface gradient of 0.020 (irrigated graycinnamonic soils) and a furrow length of 150 m, the losses are 55.88 kg/ha for humus, 4.06 kg/ha for nitrogen, 4.57 kg/ha for phosphorus, and 67.82 kg/ha for potassium at the water discharge rate of 0.2 L/s. They increase up to 247.90, 17.42, 21.44, and 352.42 kg/ha, respectively, at the water discharge rate of 0.8 L/s.

Deflation. Pastures and plowlands are subjected to wind erosion at wind velocities of about 5 m/s and higher in any season. The development of wind erosion is especially pronounced in seasons when the soil is loose, dry, and not covered by vegetation. Wind erosion is developed on winter pastures and plowed fields. It is enhanced at excessive grazing loads, improper technologies of soil cultivation, thin vegetation, and the presence of carbonates and salts in the upper soil horizons.

The air humidity and temperature exert an indirect impact on the wind erosion. It begins at the soil moistening of less than 12–15%. In the arid climate, even small changes in the wind velocity under the impact of the local conditions may cause the development of wind erosion up to dust storms. On the southeastern Shirvan and Sal'yansk steppes, local wind erosion may take place even under the impact of weak winds (5–6 m/s). Up to 50% of the substances may be blown out from the upper 15–20 cm of the soil.

The soil texture is an important factor of wind erosion. Coarse-textured (sandy) soils are particularly susceptible to wind erosion. The changes in the physico-chemical properties of sierozemic and light gray-cinnamonic soils subjected to wind erosion are the most pronounced. In the eroded soils, the content of the sand fraction in the upper layers (0–15 and 0–50 cm) increases by 10–15%, the content of the silt fractions decreases by 30–50%, and the content of the clay fractions decreases by 15–40% as compared with the non-eroded soils. On eolian hills, the amount of the sand fraction rises by up to three times; the silt and clay fractions are blown out from the soil material.

The eroded coarse-textured soils are characterized by a decrease in the humus content by 20–40%, the content of total nitrogen by 8–45%, the content of available phosphorus by 10–30%, and the content of exchangeable potassium by 10–40%. Eolian hills formed near shrubs are characterized by a lower contents of humus (by 40–70%), total nitrogen (by 20–70%), available phosphorus (by 20–60%), and exchangeable potassium (by 5–35%) in comparison with the noneroded soils.

Salinization. The development of soil salinization depends on the local topographic features, the irrigation regime, and the groundwater regime. Intense salinization of the root zone is related to degradation of irrigation systems with the development of water infiltration from the beds of unlined irrigation canals, the absence or bad work of drainage systems, and other factors. Huge losses of irrigation water due to infiltration and poor drainage of irrigated lands result in a rise of the groundwater level; in many cases, a rise in the salinity of the irrigation water is also observed. The development of secondary soil salinization is an acute problem of irrigation farming in arid regions. Soil salinization may be also related to natural processes of salt accumulation in the intermontane depressions and on the floodplains and footslopes in the arid zone.

In the past 60 years, certain changes in the environmental conditions of the Kura–Aras Lowland (climate warming, higher potential evaporation, increased activity of bottom erosion in the ravines and river valleys, and frequent floods) have led to the increased inflow of saline groundwater from the deep horizons into the Kura, Akusha, Akhsuchai, and other rivers. Anthropogenic factors (irrigation without drainage with an uncontrolled water supply, excessive moistening, and others) have resulted in the rise of the ground and irrigation water salinity by almost two times and the enhancement of salinization on irrigated lands.

In 2010, the area of salt-affected irrigated soils in the Kura–Araks Lowland reached 373 398 ha. The largest area of salt-affected soils is found on the Mugan'–Sal'yansk Steppe (169 915 ha). Salinization of the vir-

gin land in this region is caused by the arid climate, excessive grazing pressure resulting in deterioration of the plant cover, enhanced physical evaporation from the soil surface, and the rise in the groundwater level.

Salinization of irrigated lands in the Mugan'–Sal'yansk Steppe is related to irrigation with saline water from the Kura and Akusha rivers (0.52–1.46 g/L) and from the Mugansk, Azizbekov, and Sabir canals (0.46–1.98 g/L). These waters transport up to 3600–8760 and 8100–11 880 kg/ha of salts, respectively, to the irrigated fields during the growing season.

The inclined surface of the Mugan'–Sal'yansk Steppe with depressions in places, the Quaternary deposits related to transgressions and regressions of the Caspian Sea, the shallow groundwater (3.0–4.0 m and 2.0–3.0 m in places), the absence of an artificial drainage network, the water infiltration through the bottoms and walls of irrigation canals, and the recent rise in the groundwater level to critical levels favor the active development of soil salinization in this area.

The variations in the salt content in the soils of the Kura–Aras Lowland depend on the concentration of salts in the irrigation water, the degree of drainage of the territory, and the groundwater regime. The ion concentrations in the irrigation water vary within the following values (g/L): 0.224–0.353 for Cl^- , 0.099–0.171 for Ca^{2+} , 0.443–0.908 for Mg^{2+} , and 0.094–0.283 for $\text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+$.

Turbid river water and clean artesian water and water from the kyariz (qanat) underground water systems are used for irrigation. The water salinity in the main canals is higher (0.39–1.98 g/L on the average) than in the rivers (0.4–1.1 g/L). This is explained by the fact that the river water is subjected to rapid sea sonal changes in dependence on the particular weather conditions. In periods when the surface water supply (rain, snow, and others) predominates, the salinity of the river water decreases; it increases in periods with a higher portion of the groundwater supply. In canals, the water is slowly renewed and is mainly supplied from storage reservoirs. The water salinity in such reservoirs increases because of evaporation from the open surface, the discharge of wastewater, and some other factors, which greatly affects the quality of the irrigation water.

The water salinity is the highest in the Akhsuchai, Akusha, and Kura Rivers (0.6–1.46 g/L) and in the Azizbekov, Mil'sk, and Mugansk canals (0.59–1.98 g/L). The lowest water salinity is typical of the Bolgarchai, Khachinchai, Kuruchai, and Kargarchai Rivers (0.26–0.4 g/L). In some years, the water salinity in the Aras River system may rise up to 1.5 g/L. About 50–60 years ago, the water salinity in the Kura and Aras rivers was 0.4–0.6 and 0.6–0.8 g/L, respectively. It has increased by two–three times since that time [1].

The irrigation water brings 1680–11 880 kg/ha of soluble salts to the fields per growing period, which favors an increase in the area of salt-affected soils with a corresponding decrease in the yields of cotton and other crops. Taking into account the specific features of the soils in the Kura–Araks Lowland, high duties of irrigation water are not permissible there. The following measures can be recommended to control the development of soil erosion and salinization in this area:

(1) Phytomelioration of irrigated lands with the use of zonal agrotechnologies including surface planning of irrigated land, the creation of dense plant cover providing for the biological loosening of the soil by the roots and considerable supply of the soil with fresh organic matter (stubble and root remains), sowing of halophytes (*Agropyron elongatum* and *Kochia prostrata*) in the areas with saline soils, planting of trees along ditches and canals to lower the groundwater level, etc.

(2) Proper construction and maintenance of irrigation systems with due respect for the quality of the soils, their textures, and the groundwater level and salinity; irrigation canals should have waterproof beds; vertical and deep (2.5–3.5 m) horizontal drainage systems should be constructed; a more progressive method of sprinkling irrigation should be applied; and deep wells and a drainage network should be constructed in order to lower the groundwater level.

(3) The grazing pressure on pastures should be optimized; grass sowing, planting of shelterbelts, and protection of the biological diversity in natural pasture ecosystems should be organized. The processes of water and wind erosion have some features in common; similar measures are often required to control them. In particular, the growing of intermediate crops is an efficient measure to protect the soils from wind and water erosion.

In 2016–2022, mixed sowing of main and intermediate forage crops was performed as a measure to control the water and wind erosion and improve the soil fertility. This phytomeliorative measure was applied on the Shirvan steppe (Kyurdamir and Udzhaz, irrigated meadowsierozemic soil) and Gyandzha–Kazakh massif (Akstafa, irrigated graycinnamonic soil). According to the zonal recommendations, minimum tillage was applied. The scheme of crop sowing was as follows: (winter sowing) rye + vetch + rape (for green fodder) / (after harvesting) corn + soya + sorghum + amaranth 1: 1: 1: 1 (for green fodder) / (after harvesting) barley + vetch (for green fodder). Irrigation of all the crops was aimed to maintain the soil moisture in the upper 75 cm at the level of no less than 70–75% of the field capacity. Furrow irrigation was applied.

The plant cover formed by these crops on the irrigated meadowsierozemic and graycinnamonic soils was dense and favored greater accumulation of the root mass and the soil enrichment with fresh organic matter all year round (8.9–10.2 and 11.0–12.3 t/ha of air-dry mass of stubble and root remains with a high content of ash elements (1.80–5.91%), nitrogen (0.88–1.79%), phosphorus (0.48–0.89%), and potassium (0.35–1.97). The yield of the crops (in fodder units) increased by 2.5 times.

In the years with intermediate forage crops sown, the bulk density, porosity, structure, and biological characteristics of the irrigated meadowsierozemic and graycinnamonic soils were quickly restored to the normal values. The total content of dissolved solids (TDS) in water extracts from the irrigated meadowsierozemic soil (0–2 m) decreased from 0.34–0.46% at the beginning of the experiment to 0.17–0.27%. The soil bulk density decreased by 10–12% in the upper 70 cm and by 20–30% in the layer of 0–100 cm. In the irrigated graycinnamonic soil, the TDS dropped to 0.05–0.09%,

and the soil bulk density decreased by 12–15 and 25–35%, respectively. The soil washout decreased by 3–7 times.

The agrochemical characteristics of the plow layer (0–27 cm) improved in both soils. A reliable tendency for a rise in the content of humus and nitrogen by 0.38–0.40% as compared with the initial level was observed. The pool of humus increased from 67.4 to 75.5 t/ha, while the pool of nitrogen, from 5.70 to 5.94 t/ha. The available phosphorus content increased from 17–19 mg/100 g to 22–28 mg/100 g in the plow layer (0–27 cm), but it somewhat decreased in the lower (27–55 cm) layer. The content of exchangeable potassium increased from a low level to a medium level in both layers.

Base saturation plays an important role in soil fertility. The higher the base saturation, the better the physicochemical soil properties. Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} cations are good coagulators and improve the soil structure. In the plow layer of the irrigated gray-cinnamonic soil, the base saturation in aggregates <10 mm reached 67–75% (higher than moderate). In the irrigated meadow-sierozemic soil, it was somewhat lower (60–66%).

The comparison of the data on the chemical composition of the water extracts from the soils of the experimental plots obtained in 2012 and 2004 shows that the salt content in the 1m deep layer decreased to 0.145–0.165% in the irrigated meadow-sierozemic soil and to 0.07–0.12% in the irrigated gray-cinnamonic soil.

The content of agronomically valuable soil aggregates (0.25–10 mm) increased by 8.8–14.9% in the irrigated gray-cinnamonic soil and by 6.8–12.1% in the irrigated meadow-sierozemic soil. The rise in the content of water-stable aggregates was due to the structuring role of the root systems of rye, vetch, soya, rape, corn, sorghum, and amaranth; the soil enrichment with organic matter; and the high content of calcium in the remains of these plants.

Biological soil properties are important indicators of soil fertility [14]. Stubble and root remains (8.9–10.2 and 11.0–12.3 t/ha of air-dry mass of three crops in a year) admixed into the plow layer (0–27 cm) enhanced the biological activity of the soils. The total number of microorganisms increased by 1.3–1.9 times, the portion of bacteria increased by 68–74%, and the portions of actinomycetes and fungi decreased by 24.5–27.4 and 0.04–0.08%, respectively. Thus, intermediate leguminous–grass–cruciferous forage crops had a strong phytomeliorative effect.

CONCLUSIONS

(1) The geomorphologic and climatic conditions and improper management of natural pastures and irrigated lands in the Kura–Aras Lowland favor intensive development of irrigation-induced and natural water erosion, wind erosion, and salinization.

(2) Irrigation-induced erosion results in the washout of 2.23–14.86 t of soil, 56–304 kg of humus, 4–21 kg of nitrogen, and 4.6–26.6 kg of phosphorus and other nutrients per hectare during one irrigation in dependence on the slope of the furrows (0.003–0.020) and water discharge rates (1.4–0.8 L/s).

(3) Wind erosion of sierozemic and gray-cinnamonic soils results in an increase in the content of the sand fraction by 10–15% with a drop in the contents of

the silt and clay fractions by 30–50 and 1–40%, respectively; the humus content in the eroded soils decreases by 20–40%.

(4) The higher salinity of the irrigation water (up to 1.5–1.98 g/L) enhances the soil salinization. The total area of salt-affected soils has reached 373 398 ha, which is two times higher than that in 1950–1960.

(5) The optimum combination of main and intermediate forage crops with their proper distribution in space and time is an efficient measure to control water and wind erosion. It lowers soil erosion by three–seven times; ensures the significant accumulation of organic matter in the plow layer (0–27 cm); increases the biological activity of the soil by 35–40%; the pools of humus, nitrogen, and available phosphorus in the soil increase; and the soil salinity and bulk density decrease.

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